

Valdocco Vivibile: a livable district

The Torino Urban Lab coordinates the Valdocco Vivibile pilot in collaboration with the City of Torino to promote the development of climate-resilient neighborhoods through small-scale and diffused green infrastructure solutions. The pilot has three main pillars: high replicability; multifunctional interventions; and innovation in design, materials, vegetation, and mobility modes.

8.7 tons of projected
carbon
sequestration

projected increase in
3X stormwater
infiltration
capacity

Nature-based Solutions Benefits

Background

Climate change effects represent an increasingly significant reality to the city of Torino, leading to more intense and frequent heat stress and flood events. To adapt the city to climate change effects, improve livability and increase biodiversity, the Valdocco Vivibile pilot integrates micro-scale Nature-based Solutions (NbS) interventions, while working closely with stakeholders and citizens to boost awareness and dialogue. Due to the intensive CONEXUS participatory approach in the Valdocco Vivibile pilot, the community of local stakeholders supports the promotion and diffusion of the strategies and policies defined in the Climate Resilience Plan and the Green Infrastructure Plan, which were both recently approved by the City of Torino.

Challenges

Connecting with other projects in Turin.

Long-term sustainability of the Nature-based Solutions management.

Applying integrated policies in Turin.

Photos by Torino Urban Lab

The participatory process in the Valdocco Vivibile pilot

Due to climate change, Torino faces local extreme weather events, leading to increased intensity and frequency of heat stress and flooding. Given the cross-cutting nature of the risks associated with climate change, counteract measures require a multidisciplinary and integrated approach involving all levels of decision-making and collaboration with superordinate agencies. The Torino Urban Lab established an open and friendly forum in the Valdocco Vivibile pilot, where local stakeholders can meet for discussions and build a learning community. This participatory process meets multiple goals that support the implementations

in the Valdocco Vivibile pilot and city-wide, it supports NbS measures planned by the Torino Administration to adapt other neighborhoods to climate change. These goals include: informing citizens about the works and the strategic framework adopted by the city to counteract climate change risks; fostering awareness about climate change risks; boosting dialogue between stakeholders and the local administration; involving residents and other stakeholders in public debate; and the management of the NbS and other urban furniture installed as part of the NbS interventions.

Schools and young generations at the center

The participatory process accompanying our pilot focuses mainly on involving students and teachers from schools within the working area of the VV pilot.

Dedicating efforts on this target group means making future citizens understand the importance and the benefits of nature in the urban

context and developing in them a sense of ownership and positive feeling about nature and public spaces. The activities were co-designed with teachers to match the students' engagement with ongoing learning courses during the school year. The VV pilot combined training and awareness-raising initiatives with practical activities to provide scholars with a sense and the concrete functioning of nature.

Innovations in design, materials, vegetation, and new mobility modes

Torino's streetscape is largely historically defined and challenging to adapt due to strict architectural preservation regulations. The Valdocco Vivibile pilot tests the latest multifunctional design approaches that combine shading and storm

water management services, and integrate them with attractive street furniture. The goal is to develop multifunctional greenery and find retrofit opportunities by redeveloping public areas previously dedicated to urban waste collection. The concept of the Valdocco Vivibile pilot also has been designed to be replicated by producing a list of innovative materials and types of furniture, which best match the climate change challenges and the dense urban environment of the districts of Torino.

Valdocco Vivibile is part of a more comprehensive city strategy named "Resilient districts." This strategy involves innovative solutions to counter the increasing "heat island" effect and to better manage storm water during intense and more frequent

Let's manage nature together!

precipitation events, while creating a more livable and biodiverse urban environment. Specifically, it intends to reduce asphalt and impervious surfaces, converting them into green infrastructure and sustainable drainage systems that can provide shade and collect rainwater, in turn reducing flows into the grid and possible flooding. The introduced greenery and tree plantings will also slow the traffic flow. Additional measures, such as the narrowing of roadways and chicanes, further reduce the velocity of motor vehicles, while allowing cars, bicycles, and pedestrians to coexist.

Related Projects

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 Wetland Lugano pilot, Buenos Aires
<https://www.conexusnbs.com/life-labs/project-four-cckhc>
-
 ProGInreg
<https://progireg.eu/>
-
 CLIMABOROUGH
<https://climaborough.eu/>
-
 Respondent
<https://www.revesnetwork.eu/project/respondet/>

Learn more in
[conexusnbs.com](https://www.conexusnbs.com)

References

- TORINO URBAN LAB, 2023. <https://urbanlabtorino.it/>
- TORINO VIVIBILE, 2023. <https://www.torinovivibile.it/>

Key messages

1. Involve key local stakeholders and target your activities to a specific "section" of the population (e.g., pupils, traders, disabled people, etc.)
2. For effective communication and positive interactions, consider each stakeholder's own specific "language and skills" in participatory processes.
3. When planning Nature-based Solution interventions:
 - Consider long-term management and maintenance of the interventions.
 - Integrate them with other urban transformative interventions, such as draining systems, roads, footpaths, and mobility solutions.

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City Partners

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